

SOCIAL SCIENCES

AN ALTERNATIVE TO THE TRANSITION TO THE ESTONIAN MODEL OF THE PROFIT TAX OF COMMERCIAL BANKS OF GEORGIA

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Abstract

This paper examines the feasibility of transitioning to a new model of profit taxation for commercial banks in Georgia. The analysis is based on financial data from Georgian and European banks and compares effective tax rates, provisioning practices, and other relevant indicators. The study recommends strengthening horizontal monitoring between banks and tax authorities as an alternative to adopting the Estonian model of profit tax in Georgia.

Keywords: Banking Sector, Effective Tax Rate, Estonian Model, Georgia, Profit Tax.

Introduction

Georgia began implementing elements of the Estonian model in 2017. Initially, it applied to small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) with annual revenues below 10 million GEL. In 2021, the eligibility was extended to large companies. Positive impacts observed: A) Increased investment. Studies suggest the model has led to increased investment in Georgian businesses. B) Enhanced business growth. Reinvesting profits has contributed to business expansion and job creation. C) Simplified tax system. The model is seen as simpler and more transparent than the previous system. Challenges and concerns: A) Limited impact on large businesses. Some argue the model primarily benefits SMEs and has limited impact on large corporations. B) Potential for profit shifting. Concerns exist that companies might shift profits to avoid taxation. C) Potential decrease in government revenue: With delayed tax collection, government revenue might be impacted in the short term.

The Georgian banking system has witnessed significant growth in recent years, with net profits exceeding 2 billion GEL in 2021-2022. However, concerns remain regarding the relatively low effective tax rates paid by commercial banks, which average around 11.87%. This raises questions about the fairness and efficiency of the current tax system and has led to discussions about transitioning to the Estonian model of profit tax.

1. Effective Tax Rate

The general idea for estimating effective tax rates is to measure the bank's actual income tax liability relative to the size of its taxable income. If the effective tax rate is significantly lower than the statutory tax rate, it indicates that the company benefits from special tax benefits or a preferential tax regime applicable in its country of operation.

Erosion of the corporate tax base due to profit hiding is a significant and persistent problem that can lead to government spending cuts, budget deficits, and the introduction of new forms of indirect or direct taxes

to reduce corporate tax revenues. In this context, assessing the true size of profit is crucial. Quantifying the redistribution of profits provides insight into the income escaping the tax system.

It is worth noting that since 2014, European financial institutions have begun disclosing their activities by country, in accordance with the European Union Directive (Directive 2013/36/EU). These disclosures include net banking income, profit before tax, the amount of taxes paid, and the number of full-time employees for each country where the bank has a subsidiary. The data was collected manually and covers 51 European banking groups between 2014 and 2020, as well as several foreign banks operating within the EU. This new data enables us to address some crucial questions, such as: Do banks choose to have subsidiaries in low-tax locations?

Several studies have analyzed the country-by-country reporting imposed on European banks. For instance, Vincent Bouvatier, Gunther Capelle-Blancard, and Anne-Laure Delatte, in their 2019 work titled "After the Crash," used a gravity model to estimate profit shifts based on individual country reports published by the 37 largest European banks. Their research database combines OECD macro CbCR (Country-by-Country Reporting data) and micro-level CbCR data.

Even with this research, tax savings for EU banks are estimated to be between €1 billion and €3.6 billion. Notably, the study by Fatika and Gregory (2020) is closely related to this paper. Their research attempts to estimate the change in European banks' profits. However, their sample comprises 27 banks headquartered in 8 different EU countries, while the data for this study encompasses 51 European banks headquartered in 18 different European countries. Additionally, their sample spans only two years, while this study covers a broader period of seven years, from 2014 to 2020.

Furthermore, it is crucial to consider circumstances where a portion of a banking institution's profit remains untaxed or is reduced due to various factors. This includes the artificial manipulation of increased expenses or the reduction of the taxable profit base through the increase in expenses incurred during asset revaluation.

The effective tax rate is calculated as the ratio of the profit tax (Tax on profit or loss) to the pre-tax profit amount. This can be expressed as follows: Effective tax rate = Tax on profit or loss/(Profit or loss before tax).

According to official data from 2021-2022, based on the official statistics of the National Bank of Georgia

and the annual reports of leading Georgian commercial banks, an analysis of the Georgian banking system reveals an effective tax rate ranging from 7% to 16% for the five largest Georgian commercial banks, encompassing at least 5% of total assets. The average median rate stands at 11.87% (table 1). For comparison, the average global level is 26%. For example, in Spain, where the corporate tax is 19%, a leading bank, BBVA, reported an effective tax rate of 24% in 2021. Similarly, in Germany, where the corporate tax is 15%, Commerzbank, another leading bank, reported a much higher effective tax rate of 30.5% in 2022.

Table 1.

2022	Pre-Tax Profit (GEL)	TAX (GEL)	ETR, %	Tax stationary Rate, %
TBC Bank	24,135,160,161	1,156,970,328	16%	
Bank of Georgia	26,625,502,407	1,070,901,875	8%	
Liberty Bank	3,623,271,954	72,189,742	7%	
Procredit bank	1,726,760,909	55,139,005	16%	
Basis Bank	3,092,391,711	60,052,087	11%	
Total	59,203,087,142	2,415,253,038		
Share to system	84 %			
Medium			11.87 %	<15%

According to Table 1, despite having one of the highest pre-tax profit rates and being the first bank in terms of assets, "Bank of Georgia" has an average profit tax efficiency ratio of only 8%. This is even higher than the corporate profit tax rate, but still falls behind by 2 times.

The indicator for "Liberty Bank," the third largest bank in terms of assets, is practically similar. Its profit tax efficiency ratio was 7.27% in 2022 and zero in 2021.

TBC Bank has effective tax rates closer to the corporate profit tax, although it was 11% in 2021. Among the presented banks, Procredit Bank, with German capital, was relatively close to the current tax norm, with a range of 14-16%. In terms of net budget losses, based on the profit tax level, the budget losses at least 290 million GEL.

2. Net Income Before Provisions (Operating Profit) Efficiency Rate:

Another coefficient used to assess tax payment efficiency is the Net Income Before Provisions (Operating Profit) Efficiency Rate. This rate is directly related to the commercial bank's net profit and the profit tax efficiency rate. It is calculated as the ratio of Total Provisions for Possible Losses to Net Income Before Provisions.

As is known, the reserve for possible losses of assets is a reserve account established for a commercial bank's assets. It represents the amount intended to cover potential losses of loan and non-loan assets and contingent liabilities. This reserve includes both special and common reserves. This issue is regulated in international banking practice by special provisions on asset classification and the creation of special reserves.

Similarly, in Georgia, the instruction "On the Approval of the Rules for the Classification of Assets and the Creation and Use of Reserves for Possible

Losses by Commercial Banks" is in force. This instruction was issued on the basis of a relevant order from the President of the National Bank.

Commercial banks are obligated to spend the created reserves and any subsequent increases in expenses under the "Loss according to Possible Losses of Assets" category. This will be shown on their balance sheets under the "Reserves for Possible Losses of Assets" line. Additionally, according to the risk classification of assets, the necessary reserves must be created during the accounting period, regardless of the income received.

The main problem here is twofold. On the one hand, there is the market price formation for real estate, and on the other hand, the sale price of the property, including sales to third parties. Not infrequently, the property is sold at auction at a lower price, which increases the amount to be reserved and reduces the profit tax.

The Net Income Before Provisions (Operating Profit) Efficiency Rate shows the ratio between reserved funds and profit before provisioning. This is important to the extent that reserved funds are carried out in expenses, as a high rate reduces the taxable profit base. For comparison, the indicators of individual banks are used in relation to the average system indicator, as well as by individual banks in relation to the banking systems of other countries. The said coefficient is calculated as:

$$\text{Net Income before Provisions effective rate} = \frac{\text{Total Provisions for Possible Losses}}{\text{Net Income before Provisions}}$$

These two coefficients are complementary. In general, a bank's tax base can be considered normal if both conditions are met: the effective tax rate is higher than the current corporate tax rate, and the effective rate

of profit before provisions is also low, ideally lower than the profit rate itself.

Diagram 1. Effective tax rates in leading commercial banks, 2022, %

Source: National bank of Georgia, Annual reports of listing banks

Diagram 1 shows that the effective tax rates of Georgia's leading commercial banks, whose assets exceed 5% of the total system and constitute 84% of the system's assets, are lower than the current corporate tax in 2022. The average effective tax rate for these banks is 18%. Notably, the rate is significantly lower for the top 3 system-forming banks. TBC Bank's rate is 7%, while Bank of Georgia's is 16%.

For the effective tax rate of profit before provisioning, the average rate is higher than the current rate and almost twice the average system rate of 28%. Procredit Bank is the only bank with a rate close to the potential tax rate.

Losses based on possible asset losses arise from the provision of negatively classified assets. Among these losses, even the two leading systemic commercial banks, which own 74% of the banking sector's assets, experience an average of 90% loan losses. The loss in terms of investment fees is practically zero, which is natural due to commercial banks' small investment portfolios and the underdeveloped capital market.

In general, losses on possible asset losses mainly come from loan losses and other asset losses, which periodically increase in percentage terms.

For comparison, we can look at the data of European banks. EU Tax Observatory Working Paper No. 9, issued in 2022, estimates that the effective tax rate for all European banks, combining both tax and non-tax havens, is 19.6%, based on a sample of 5271 institutions. This is lower than the legislated tax rate of 22.9%.

However, for relatively large and system-forming individual commercial banks, the effective tax rates are higher than the statutory tax rates. For example, according to the 2022 financials of Komerční banka, one of the leading Czech banks, the effective tax rate was 18.3%, and the effective rate of profit before provisions was 5%, with a corporate profit rate of 19%. Komerční banka's net interest margin is 2.42%.

Similarly, RABO Bank, a leading Dutch bank, reported an effective tax rate of 26% and an effective rate of profit before provisions of 5% in its 2022 financial data, with a corporate profit rate of 24%. The net interest margin of RABO Bank is 1.35%.

Finally, BBVA, a well-known Spanish bank, had an effective tax rate of 31% and an effective rate of profit before provisions of 20% in its 2021 financial data, with a corporate profit rate of 25%. BBVA's net interest margin is -0.45%.

As this analysis shows, the Georgian banking sector's tax risk profile is significantly higher than that of European banks. This high tax risk is linked to both high credit risk and high lending rates compared to the annual growth of the gross domestic product, which is discussed in detail in the relevant part of the report.

The objectivity of the taxable profit base calculation is a separate issue, particularly relevant for the pre-provisioning profit portion. It is important for Georgian commercial banks, which report to the National Bank using the IFRS standard, to strengthen horizontal monitoring to reduce tax risk. This refers to balanced cooperation with tax authorities regarding corporate taxes, including a transition to a platform of mutual trust and transparent communication, which is an accepted practice in EU countries.

In European countries, commercial banks have a tax department responsible for all tax affairs and even strategy development, along with the internal audit committee. While a similar structure exists in Georgian commercial banks, we believe that improving and expanding horizontal monitoring is a matter of urgency.

3. Net Interest Margin and its Impact on Tax Policy

The primary determinant of any bank's performance is the net interest margin (NIM). This ratio represents the net interest income relative to the average working assets. In other words, the interest spread should cover losses on the reserve for possible loan losses (PLL), taxes, and interest costs on raised funds. It's noteworthy that Georgian banks have a significantly higher net interest margin compared to European banks.

The net interest margin reflects two key aspects:

- Ratio of net interest income to bank assets: This indicates the rate of return on profit to assets.
- Real spread of interest income and expenses: This shows the difference between the

interest income generated and the interest expense incurred.

The high interest margin in Georgia stems from two primary factors:

- High credit risk: This risk is significantly higher compared to European countries.
- High tax risks: While credit risk receives more emphasis in Georgian commercial banks' risk management, tax risks deserve greater attention and effort.

For comparison, the global average net interest margin across all types of banks in 135 countries was 3.61% in 2020. In contrast, Georgian banks recorded a 5.3% net interest margin, the highest globally. The highest value was observed in Zimbabwe (12.83%),

and the lowest in Iraq (0.17%). In 40 European countries, the average net interest margin in 2020 was 1.97%, with the highest in Moldova (4.79%) and the lowest in France (0.52%).

While the Georgian commercial banks' net interest margin decreased to 5.3% by the end of 2022, it still remains considerably high. Compared to European countries, including Moldova (4.79%), Turkey (3.29%), and Ukraine (3.69%), Georgian banks still have a relatively high net interest margin as of 2021.

4. Net Profit Growth Exceeds Asset Growth

The net profit of the Georgian banking system grew 2.4 times between 2018 and 2022, significantly exceeding the 77% increase in assets during the same period. In 2018, the total assets were 39.6 billion GEL, and by 2022, they had reached 70.3 billion GEL.

Diagram 2. Annual profit in the joint banks of Georgia, 2021-2022 %

Source: National Bank of Georgia

In contrast, the indicators of return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) in Georgia's leading commercial banks are significantly higher than the European average.

The global average ROA in 2021, based on data from 136 countries, was 1.57%. The highest value was observed in Syria (8.83%), and the lowest in Greece (-1.82%). In Europe, the 2021 average across 41 countries was 0.87%, with the highest rate in Moldova (2.34%) and the lowest again in Greece (-1.82%).

Regarding the bank's ROE, the European average in 2021 across 41 countries was 12.72%. Kazakhstan had the highest value at 34.96%, followed by Georgia at 26.18%. In other European countries, such as Estonia (9.26%), Bulgaria (10.5%), Hungary (11.43%), Turkey (12.68%), Ukraine (12.25%), Lithuania (12.98%), Romania (14.86%), and Azerbaijan (16.27%), the rate was lower than in Georgia.

Furthermore, this trend is even more pronounced among the leading Georgian commercial banks. In 2021-2022, TBC Bank's ROE was 36.12%, and Bank of Georgia's ROE was 37.6%. This is significantly higher than the average rate of systemic banks (26%) and surpasses other countries such as Azerbaijan (16.27%), Moldova (14.05%), Belarus (9.47%), and Turkey (12.68%). However, the profit tax indicator shows less correlation with profit growth rates, as is evident from the efficiency indicators discussed earlier.

5. Pre-Tax Profit Margin

Pre-tax profit margin is another important indicator used to assess the profitability of banks. It reflects how effectively taxes are paid based on the company's total turnover. Several methods can be used to calculate profit margin, depending on the desired level of profit measurement (gross profit, operating profit, profit before tax, or net profit).

Pre-tax profit margin (margin) indicates the percentage of profit (or loss) before tax liability relative to the total turnover. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Pre-Tax Profit Margin} = \frac{\text{Profit or Loss Before Tax}}{\text{Turnover}}$$

The pre-tax profit margin indicator allows banks in different countries to assess how much their profit is burdened by taxes. It helps them identify whether they are effectively utilizing their profits for tax purposes or if they are engaging in artificial manipulations to reduce their tax burden.

Additionally, the pre-tax profit margin can be compared to the net profit margin to identify the difference between the two. A significant difference indicates a high profit tax burden. This relationship holds true, assuming no unforeseen costs significantly impact the net profit.

As shown in Diagram 3, the leading three banks within the system-forming group generated a total income of 6.3 billion GEL, representing 92% of the total income for this group. Their pre-tax profit amounted to 2.3 billion GEL,

Diagram 3. Total revenue and profit before tax 2021-2022

Source: National Bank of Georgia,

This means that the ratio between turnover and profit is higher in banks with lower costs. These costs include not only regular expenses but also unforeseen events that can reduce the net profit. Conversely, the

ratio is lower in banks with high profit deviations or significant costs. In the context of banking institutions, such expenses can include provisioning expenses for potential loan losses.

Diagram 4. Pre-tax and net profit margins of Georgian banks, %

Source: National Bank of Georgia

As shown in Diagram 4, large commercial banks like Bank of Georgia and TBC Bank operate with a turnover four times higher than the system average. Consequently, their profit margin based on the net enterprise scale effect is also higher than the system average. While the percentage difference between their margins and the systemic average (5%) is slightly higher, it is not significant. For TBC Bank, the difference is 7%, and for Bank of Georgia, it is 5%.

For comparison, we can look at the data of European banks. According to the 2022 financials of BBVA, a leading Czech bank, the pre-tax profit margin was 42% and the net profit margin was 26%. The leverage is quite high at 16%, with a corporate profit rate of 19%.

Similarly, RABO Bank, another leading Dutch bank we reviewed, reported a pre-tax profit margin of 30% and a net profit margin of 22%, with a 24% corporate profit rate. The pre-tax profit margin was

quite high, and the percentage difference with the net interest margin was 8%.

6. Bank Tax Structure

A comparative analysis of Georgian commercial banks and leading foreign banks from the perspective of tax structure during the pre-COVID pandemic period (2017-2019) reveals an interesting picture. The income tax of bank employees holds the highest share in the Georgian banking sector's tax structure, accounting for 51%. The share of profit tax is on average 34%, and VAT comes in third with a 9% share. This trend has continued into the current year (Diagram #5).

However, it is important to note that financial services provided in European countries are exempt from VAT. In contrast, the collection, which is included in financial services in Georgia, is considered separate in European countries and therefore subject to VAT. This is because international legislation does not classify it as a financial service.

Diagram 5. Tax structure of Georgian banks, 2017-2019, GEL

Table 2.

Different indicators				
		2017	2019	
Income Tax	73,680,990.30	34%	97,285,259.70	39%
VAT	24,403,225.00	11%	25,748,602.00	10%
Bank Tax	110,794,154.40	51%	118,039,781.20	48%
Contribution	7,463,820.10	3%	6,233,984.00	3%
	216,342,189.80	100%	247,307,626.90	100%

If we compare these data with the tax figures of the leading Dutch bank RABO Bank (Diagram 6), we can see that 54% comes from profit tax, and the share of VAT is 18%, and the share of contributions, including contributions to pension funds and other The share of bank charges is -25%.

Diagram 6. Tax structure of RABO Bank, 2017, mln. Euro

7. Current Effective Tax Rate

Another way to measure effective tax rates is through the current effective tax rate. Similar to the effective tax rate but focusing on current tax obligations, it is calculated as the ratio of current tax on profits to pre-tax profits:

$$\text{Current Effective Tax Rate} = \frac{\text{Current Tax on Profit or Loss}}{\text{Profit or Loss Before Tax}}$$

Income tax expenses encompass both current tax expenses (taxes paid regardless of future developments) and deferred tax expenses (taxes on profits or tax benefits from losses that will be paid in future years, sometimes depending on future occurrences).

Companies may sometimes enter into special arrangements to postpone paying taxes indefinitely or for a very long time. This can lead to an increase in the income tax base through deferred taxes. Conversely, a company (or bank) can use future tax benefits to decrease its tax expenses, including deferred tax liabilities. Non-taxable one-off expenses can also reduce the taxable profit base.

Calculating the current effective tax rate (excluding deferred taxes) is only possible if banks distinguish between current and deferred income tax expense in their financial data. The leading Georgian system-forming bank, Bank of Georgia,

Table 3.

Different indicators for 2020, 2021, 2022 years			
	2022	2021	2020
Current income tax expense	137,430	111,652	4,539
Deferred income tax (expense)	53,221	36,828	26,094
Profit tax (expense)	190,651	74,824	21,555

The income tax rate applied to most of the income of Georgian banking groups is the same as the income tax rate applied to the income of subsidiaries, ranging from 15% to 25% (2021: 15% to 25%, 2020: 15% to 25%). For reference, on June 12, 2018, a change to the current corporate taxation model applied to financial institutions, including banks and insurance businesses, came into force.

The change involves a zero corporate tax rate on undistributed profits and a 15% corporate tax rate on distributed profits effective January 1, 2023. Under the amendment, which will take effect on January 1, 2023, the existing taxation rules for financial institutions, including banks, will remain unchanged. Additionally, from 2023, the current corporate tax rate for banks will increase from 15% to 20%. Furthermore, beginning in 2023, taxable interest income and deductible expected credit losses (ECLs) on customer loans will be determined by International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) instead of SEB local regulations.

Transitional differences in ECLs will be taxed at a one-time rate of 15%. The amended law does not define "transitory differences in interest income." This change had an immediate effect on the deferred tax asset and deferred tax liability attributable to previously recognized temporary differences arising from prior periods.

For example, in the case of Bank of Georgia, the balances of deferred tax assets and liabilities were restated as of December 31, 2022, in accordance with the updated legislation. This change resulted in a substantial one-time deferred tax charge, as banks previously recognized deferred tax only to the extent they expected to do so until January 1, 2023.

The effective income tax rate is different from the statutory income tax rates. As of December 31, 2022, December 31, 2021 and December 31, 2020, a reconciliation of income tax expense at statutory rates and actual expense is as follows:

Table 4.

Different indicators for 2020, 2021, 2022 years

	2022	2021	2020
Profit before income tax expense	1,634,650	801,942	316,498
Statutory tax rate in Georgia	15%	15%	15%
Theoretical income tax expense at average tax rate	245,198	120,291	47,475
Non-taxable income	115,636	50,671	35,910
Non-deductible expenses	3,229	2,931	6,425
Correction of prior year declarations	2,846	15	3,343
Tax at the domestic rates applicable to profits in each country	1,991	2,401	525
Effects from changes in tax legislation	53,074		
Other	51	143	303
Income tax expense	190,651	74,824	21,555
Effective tax rate	12%	9.3%	6.8%

Taxes in Georgia and Belarus include corporate income tax (profit tax), personal income tax, property tax, and value-added tax. This creates significantly higher tax risks in these countries compared to those with more developed tax systems.

The provided example clearly demonstrates that, over the past three years, the current effective tax rate, including deferred taxes, has remained low at an average of 7% per year. This is nearly two times lower than the official profit tax rate of 15%.

Conclusion:

Our research indicates that Georgian commercial banks operate under high spreads and interest margins. While this insures risks like potential asset losses, it also leads to high lending rates. This, in turn, can trigger increased asset losses and reduced taxable profits. Furthermore, effective tax rates for Georgia's leading system-forming commercial banks are significantly lower than the European average, both for the entire banking system and individual banks.

The Georgian banking system operates with higher banking concentration and lending interest rates than the European average. This ensures high profitability for the system, but it also indicates a low level of competition. One of the main challenges for the development of the banking sector should be to increase competition, including preventing the entry of European banks into the Georgian banking market.

Additionally, we believe that reducing interest rates would be more effectively achieved through non-interest expense optimization rather than additional tax benefits. While the proportion of non-interest expenses in total revenues is lower in Georgian banks than the European average, due to low salaries, banks can adjust their non-interest expense structure by improving digital platforms. This would also increase non-interest income.

Specifically, the distributed profit rule, effective January 1, 2023, will maintain existing taxation rules for financial institutions, including banks. Additionally, the current corporate tax rate for banks will increase from 15% to 20% starting in 2023. We believe this increase is justified, and the banking sector does not need further tax liberalization incentives. The Estonian model of profit tax, which allows reinvested profits to be used for working capital, has proven effective in stimulating business, particularly for medium and small businesses. However, this issue is less relevant to the banking sector today. The main obstacle preventing interest rate reductions lies in insufficient banking competition, as mentioned earlier.

The current tax model of the Georgian banking system already provides a high return on capital and assets, ensuring investor attractiveness and facilitating access to credit resources from international markets. Therefore, under the existing high interest margin conditions, increasing the effective tax rate to 20%

would have minimal impact on reducing loan interest rates, which remains the primary focus.

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